

METHODOLOGY OF STUDENTS' CREATIVE ACTIVITY DEVELOPMENT IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING PAINTING SCIENCE

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Abstract. In this article, the art of painting has been popular in the world since ancient times. The magnificent buildings built by our ancestors in the past have not lost their charm to this day. The exquisite designs continue to amaze us until now. *Naqsh* means "flower" in Arabic, and it refers to decorations made by repetition of bird, animal, flora, geometric and various other shapes in a certain order.

Keywords: fascinating jilva, bird, animal, flora, plant-like, geometric patterns, floral, group, symbolic, title writing (epigraphic), folk decorative art, continuity of national traditions, from grandfather to father, from father to son, natural luster of colors, rich creative fantasy, exquisite form, material texture, ceilings, silent vodkas, palace pillars, mosques, schools.

The painting art of Central Asia has been known to the world since ancient times. The magnificent buildings built by our ancestors have not lost their charm to this day. The exquisite designs continue to amaze us until now. *Naqsh* means "flower" in Arabic, and it is a decoration created by repetition of bird, animal, flora, geometric and various other shapes in a certain order.

What are the types of patterns? Patterns are divided into vegetal, geometric, floral, group, symbolic and other types according to their content.

Figure 1.

As a result of submitting to the requirements of Islam, the depiction of animals, birds and people disappeared, and painting flourished. The Arabic script has been mastered. As a result, the

style of title writing (epigraphy) with patterns appeared. Arabic script was drawn along with the patterns. Arabic writing served as both decoration and incantations.

Painting as a type of folk decorative art has been an important part of Uzbek culture since ancient times. Its artistic traditions have been created and developed over many centuries. Unlike all other types of art, patterns show the closeness of generations and continuity of national traditions. The traditions of painting have been passed down from grandfather to father and from father to son as methods of learning this type of art. Thanks to this continuity, the art of painting has been preserved until now. The best examples of the pattern are distinguished by the expediency and beauty of the forms combined through a rich creative imagination.

Artistic painting is the art of creating beauty in the harmony of colors and unique compositions. In his work, the master painter skillfully uses the natural luster and harmony of colors, the beautiful shape, and the texture of the material to achieve vivid expression.

In the traditional architecture of Uzbekistan, painting is mainly used to decorate ceilings, silent vodkas, palace pillars, mosques, schools, houses of the rich, and wooden products. The rhythmic movement of intertwined branches, branches and luxuriously depicted flowers in delicate plant-geometric patterns, classical motifs of Uzbek masters' work and girikh patterns are adapted to the shape of the ceilings. The pattern serves to decorate more interiors and covered porches and porches.

Currently, the pattern is used in architecture, home furnishings, gifts, small wooden toys, musical instruments and household items.

The art of artistic painting is gaining popularity nowadays. Through the press, radio, television, cinema, people get acquainted with these art examples and their folk masters. Among these artists are O. Kasimjonov, Ye. Raufov, A. Boltayev, S. Norkoziyev, A. Azimov, A. Isayev, B. Abdullayev, T. Tokhtakho'jayev, J. Khakimov, Z. Bositkhanov. , M. Torayev, T. Ahmedov, K. Karimov, A. Ilhomov and others. The works of our national masters and their apprentices can be seen in the Museum of Applied Arts in Tashkent, in exhibition halls, art salons, as well as in residential and public buildings, for example, the Tashkent State Circus, Alisher Navoi Opera and Ballet Theater, It can be seen in administrative and household facilities such as the National Academic Drama Theater, the Museum of the History of the Timurids, the Oliy Majlis and City Hall buildings, metro stations, hotels, etc. Currently, the task is to expand the network of clubs in schools and extracurricular institutions as much as possible. Studying the art of folk painting serves to develop artistic taste, hard work in students and acquire a number of useful knowledge and skills. It helps to identify and develop their creative abilities.

Painting schools. During the period of the Khanate, masters of folk art began to gather in cities such as Khiva, Kokan, Bukhara, and Samarkand. Fergana and Bukhara painters often came to Samarkand, Kokan and Margilan masters came to Tashkent to decorate many buildings. This plays a very important role in the further development of painting schools, the creation of unique compositions, and the enrichment of the color complex. Although these patterns are similar to each other, each school of painting is distinguished by its own composition, work style, and color scheme.

Tashkent school of painting. Tashkent patterns are distinguished by their elegance and the gradual transition of colors to each other, strict adherence to a certain color scheme, and the frequent use of geometric and plant-like patterns. Patterns are often made in green gamma. In

Islamic patterns, intricate girih patterns with clearly stylized moonflower, cotton, cloth, three leaves, shukufta, leafy flower and other elements are also widely used.

The founders of the Tashkent school of painting are Olimjon Kasimjanov, Yakubjon Raufov, Jalil Khakimov, Toir Tokhtakhojayev, Zakir Bositkhanov, Makhmud Torayev, Anvar Ilhomov, Kamil Karimov, among the painters.

Figure 2.

Yo. Raufov created wonderful compositions while preserving the traditions of the Tajik school of painting. The artist skillfully used the rich cultural heritage of Uzbek-Tajik patterns and created many Islamic and geometric pattern compositions. Its patterns are distinguished by the brightness of colors and harmony with each other. He discovered new elements in his compositions. Yo. Raufov exaggerated the patterns and used the kundal technique. T. Tokhtakhojayev was able to create intricate pattern compositions. The pattern of the master in golden-brown color was a new step in the development of the Tashkent school of painting.

People's Artist of Uzbekistan Jalil Khakimov, a talented student of Olimjon Kasimjanov, who made an effective contribution to the development of the Uzbek school of painting, created a unique school of painting, and is a teacher of many students. The services of the master are great in restoring the patterns created by our ancestors since ancient times. If we pay attention to the patterns of J. Khakimov, the patterns in it are rich in elements, clear, smooth, bright green in color. He worked a lot with floral compositions. J. Khakimov is an artist who mastered the traditions of Uzbek national painting art and effectively continued it. The sofa, chair, box and other items carved by the master are highly valued in many countries of the world. His work developed in the spirit of Eastern traditions and left an indelible mark in history.

Khiva school of painting. Khiva pattern is completely different from Samarkand, Tashkent, Fergana, Bukhara pattern. Blue and green colors are mostly used in Khiva pattern. In the composition of the Islamic pattern, it consists of a branch, a flower, a rose, a leaf, a pea, a flower, and a simple moon. Often star-forming gyrikhs are used, enriched with a spiral Islamic motif. Khiva patterns are generally made on the basis of Madokhil patterns. The Islamic pattern is made in small spirals. Abdulla Boltayev, Rozimat Masharipov, Adamboy Yakubov, Eshmurod Sapayev and others are prominent representatives of the Khiva school of painting.

Figure 3.

Bukhara and Samarkand painting schools. Bukhara pattern is distinguished by the complexity and attractiveness of its compositions. Bukhara patterns are distinguished by the use of complex gyriks in precise and precise sizes, and the special attention paid to the rhythm of leaves, fruits, and flowers.

Figure 4.

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